

BANDITRY AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: 2015-2021

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Abstract

The study was set to solve the problem of insecurity, particularly banditry as the crime emerged at the most critical time in the history of Nigeria and has become an uphill task for the government to tackle for the safety of lives and property of Nigerians. To solve this problem, this research has set the objective to examine the effect of banditry on agricultural production in Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted, while human needs theory was employed in the study. The population of the study was 1300, and with a sample size of 306. Data collected were from primary and secondary sources and analyzed statistically using simple percentage tables and chi-square computations. The finding revealed that the effect of banditry on agricultural production in Nigeria is negative. In order to stem the tide, if not to completely exterminate bandits from farmlands in Nigeria, especially in the northern part of the country, the study recommended that government should employ proactive measures based on international best practices, like training and retraining of officers, overhauling and equipping of the military forces with world-class ammunitions, deployment and redeployment of officers from their military base, etc.

Keywords: Bandits, Banditry, Socio-economic, Socio-economic Development.

1. Introduction

The phenomenon of banditry has emerged at the most critical time in the history of Nigeria and has become an uphill task for the government to handle for the sake of safety of lives and property of the citizenry. But, despite all efforts of government over the years to curb insecurity in the country, new phenomena keep showing up in attempt to destabilize the government and enrich a few individuals in the course of that. In recent times, particularly between 2015 and 2021, within which period this research focused, many problems have been identified; Low agricultural production, declined in general educational development and restriction of general mobility.

There are many notable security challenges that have affected Nigeria from time to time. Some of these challenges include; Kidnapping, militancy, (Islamist) in the North East; Biafra (separatist) in the South East; Niger Delta Avengers in the South-South, etc. However, Boko Haram group remains Nigeria's biggest security threat, particularly in the North East. For many years now, it has been observed that insecurity in Nigeria has increased due to banditry. These Bandits possess a significant threat to neighbouring countries as well, which in turn results in economic, social and humanitarian consequences.

Some states in the North West, like Kaduna, Katsina and Zamfara are mostly affected by arm bandits who have killed so many people and equally damaged their properties worth millions of Naira. Furthermore, the insecurity has affected socio-economic development of the country. It has also increased the incidence of forced migration, food insecurity, cattle rustling, health challenges, displacement and even death. The bandits like to carry out their crimes in isolated areas such as, villages, market squares, places of worship, etc. For instance, in Zamfara state, the former Governor Abdul aziz adopted a measure in May (2015) that brought peace and security in the state with amnesty programme and peace-deal with the bandits.

The activities of bandits have brought severe negative consequences on the agricultural production, general educational development, and general mobility, causing unprepared migration, displacement and trading. From July through December, 2021 over 343 persons died as a result of banditry, communal clashes, violent attack and reprisals, the rural economies of frontline areas which is sustained by crops and livestock farming have nearly collapsed due to bandit attack. Rural development is an essential phenomenon in realization of sustainable national development. Urban development serves as foundation of which national development is built, considering the recent increase in banditry incident, it can be obviously seen that it has grossly affected the socio-economic development in the affected States such as, Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, in particular, and the country in general.

2. Statement of the problem

As earlier stated in the introduction, the phenomenon of banditry has emerged at the most critical time in the history of Nigeria and has become an uphill task for the federal government to handle for the sake of safety of lives and property of the citizenry. But, it is observed that, despite all efforts of government over the years to curb insecurity in the country, new phenomena keep showing up in attempt to destabilize the government while serving as a conduit to enrich a few individuals as long as their activities persist. In recent times, particularly between period of 2015. and 2021, within which this research focused, many problems bothering on this topic

have been identified. These include: food insufficiency, declined in general educational development and restriction of general mobility.

The major threat to the agricultural sector in Nigeria is insecurity from both the Boko Haram and Fulani herdsmen. In the northeast of Nigeria, the sustained terrorist and banditry activities of the Boko Haram have had negative impact on agricultural activities and farming system. Not only are farming activities incapable of being carried out under an insecure environment, domestic agricultural production is stifled, farming communities are displaced and access to regional market is blocked (Eigegeand Cooke, 2016).

In addition to the Boko Haram group, the Fulani herdsmen have become a major threat to farming communities due to incessant attacks on these communities with attendant fatalities. The heinous banditry attacks carried out on these farming regions by the Fulani pastoral has made it difficult for farmers in these regions to go their farms to either plant or harvest. Aside the physical attack on the farmers, the damages carried out by the livestock (cows, cattle, etc) of these herdsmen deepens the sore of helpless farmers.

The impact of this on the economy is reflecting in the undaunted rise in the prices of food commodities, scarcity of some food items and adverse food insecurity as areas of which food items are produced are no longer producing. This because most of the farmers in agriculturally famous community of the middle belt, northwest and northeast have abandoned their farms and migrate to other communities in seeking safety for their lives hence leaving their farms fallow and unharvested crops which would pose adverse effect on the farming system. Therefore, it is against this backdrop that this study seeks to examine the effect of banditry on agriculture in Nigeria.

In the South West region, there are also dangerous spots of highway robbery and banditry along major roads in Osun, Ondo, Ogun, Ekiti, Oyo, Lagos and Edo states; they are notorious for kidnapping. In the core Niger Delta region, highway banditry is more pronounced on East-West road axis and Ode Bride axis. Likewise, in the South East region, major roads from Ebonyi, Enugu, Imo, Abia and Anambra states, there are hotspots for kidnapping and armed robbery. Highway banditry across the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria is horrifying which could leave the travelers with bitter tales to narrate, if they are lucky enough to escape alive to tell their stories.

Highway banditry connotes the vices wickedly performed by gangster gunmen on the major roads as hijackers and road marauders made up of ethnic militias, ruffians and robbers that deprive commuters of their property and life. This roving brigandage and banditry along the Nigerian highways are perpetuated despite outlaws and

men of the underworld that rob commuters of their property by force. This issue of highway banditry is worrisome and a serious growing security challenge in Nigeria that the government and the security agencies need to address, before Nigeria becomes a lawless country that do not promote ease of doing business to both national and foreign interests. It is obvious that if armed herdsmen, robbers and bandits abduct, rob and murder travelers on the major highways in Nigeria, while the government and security agencies look the other way, it would give the country a bad name and image, and could equally discourage potential investors to come and invest in the Nigerian economy. In the recent history of Nigeria, no fewer than 133 highways across the six geopolitical zones in the country have been identified as major hotspots and flashpoints for banditry, kidnapping and allied criminal vices (Amaize and Dayo, 2019). Traveling on these roads at night without security may be dangerous because chances are that one may be robbed, abducted, maimed or even killed.

In recent time, there is no week that people do not have bad experiences on these major highways in the hands of suspected herdsmen, armed robbers and kidnappers. Investigation by Amaize and Dayo (2019) revealed about 11 spots across five states in the South East region, while 41 hot beds were found to exist in the South West geopolitical zone. In the Nigeria Delta region, 28 major dangerous spots of highway robbery were taken note of. In the North West zone 20 dangerous roads and spots were noted where armed bandit deprives travelers of their belongings. Likewise, in the North central geo-political zone, no fewer than 33 volatile roads experience highway terror and banditry. In the North east region under the menace of Boko Haram terrorists, the major roads are notorious for banditry and kidnapping.

3. Objective of the Study

The main objective of this research is to unravel the activities of banditry and how they have impacted on the socio-economic development in Nigeria between the period of 2015 and 2021, with particular focus on the effects of banditry on agricultural production in Nigeria.

4. Research Question

For the purpose of eliciting responses from respondents, the following question was asked:

What are the effects of banditry on agricultural production in Nigeria?

5. Research Hypothesis

In order to be able to carry out empirical verifications and statistical calculations in this study, a null (H_0) hypothesis was postulated, hence:

H_0 : The effects of banditry seem negative on agricultural production in Nigeria.

6. **Significance to the study**

- i. This research work will be of great significance and benefits to the government, by bringing to their knowledge a way of curbing attacks by banditry in the country.
- ii. It will also serve as a reference material to scholars, students and researchers who may want to carry out further studies on this topic.
- iii. This study will also suggest ways on how to curtail the activities of banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework

1. **General Literature on the Concept of Banditry**

Conceptually, banditry is a derivative of the term bandit meaning an unlawful armed group terrorizing people and confiscating their properties. It is synonymous with the establishment of gang groups who use small and light weapons to carry out attacks against people. In this regard, banditry could mean a set-up criminal activity deliberately designed and carried out for personal gains. Due to the complex nature of bandits' activities, Egwu (2016) in a restricted manner, described banditry as a practice of stealing cattle and animals from herders or raiding of cattle from their ranches. In the same vein, banditry is reflected in criminal escapades like cattle rustling, kidnapping, armed robbery, drug abuse, arson, rape and the brazen and gruesome massacre of people of agrarian communities with sophisticated weapons by suspected herdsman and reprisal attacks from surviving victims, a development that has been brought to the front burner of national security (Uche and Iwuamadi, 2018). In his perception, Shalangwa (2013) regards banditry as the practice of raiding and attacking victims by members of an armed group, whether or not premeditated, using weapons of offence or defense, especially in semi-organized groups for the purpose of overpowering the victim and obtaining loot or achieving some political goals. Such bandits are usually perceived as outlaws, desperate and lawless marauders who do not have a definite residence or destination but roam around the forest and mountains to avoid being identified, detected and arrested.

However, where the term banditry is connected to rural, it implies a group of rural outlawed involved in illicit activities such as raiding of villages, kidnappings and Cattle rustling for primitive accumulation of wealth. Thus, bandits are gang groups terrorizing and dispossessing local people or travelers of their valuable items or properties such as merchandise, money, cattle, camel, and sheep, among others. They Operate within and along rural borders with the assistance of their local collaborators opcluding in some cases, state agents deployed to work for the safety and security of the people (Abdullahi, 2019). In another sense, banditry refers to the incidences of armed robbery or allied evolves the such as kidnapping, cattle rustling and village or market raids. It involves the use of force, or threat to that effect to

Intimidate a person or a group of persons in order to rob, rape or kill (Okoli and Okpaleke, 2014) Economic or political interests motivate banditry.

The former refers to banditries motivated by the imperative of material accumulation While the latter has to do with those driven by the quest to rob, to assault or to liquidanc a person or a group of persons based on political or ideological dispositions d and Ugwu, 2019) Thus banditry, in the context of this work, is defined as the totality of incidences of armed robbery or allied violent crimes, such as kidnapping, cattle fustling, village raids as well as highway raids which involves the use of force, of threat to that effect, to intimidate a person or a group of persons in order to rob, rape. kidnap or kill the victims

Banditry is a serious crime that poses a security challenge to democratic governance and peaceful coexistence in Nigeria. The prevalence of under-governed spaces where the government's control is ineffective and limited is a major factor giving rise to banditry. Such areas are characterized by bad governance, weak legitimacy, protracted conflict, and poor leadership, which makes citizens vulnerable to exploitation by terrorist groups, traffickers, and other criminal elements. Such areas are not generally entirely devoid of the government's control but are governed poorly and differently from larger communities. These poorly governed territories are plagued by bandits and other criminal gangs due to their remoteness, which allows for the perpetuation of an array of illegal business activities. It is not uncommon to find human trafficking, piracy, cattle rustling, and illegal mining in such areas. These areas are used to promote and sustain an illegal, informal economy. Examples of such include large forests in Rumah/Kukar Jangarai, Kamuku. Balmo, Katsina, Kaduna, Bauchi, and Kano states. Meanwhile, the Nigerian police are generally understaffed and poorly equipped, leaving them incapable of promoting security under-governed spaces, in a major factor that encourages criminality in these areas.

2. Concept of Development

The concept of development includes many aspects and has changed over time. Development is one of the main priorities of the United Nations. Development is a multidimensional undertaking to achieve a higher quality of life for all people. It includes Economic development, social development, and environmental protection are interdependent and mutually reinforcing components of sustainable development.

Development according to Oxford online dictionary is a specific state of growth or advancement. Development is a form of social change that leads to progress, acquiring knowledge and having access to resources for decent living. Development can be perceived as improvement in the lives of a people at the individual and societal levels. According to Rabie (2016). development is a comprehensive societal levels. According to Rabie (2016), development is a comprehensive societal process

to move the underdeveloped from their state of economic backwardness and scie socio-cultural change to a dynamthe state characterized by sustained economa growth and socio-cultural and pohtical transformation that improves quality of life of all

3. **The Concept of Economic Development**

Economic development is taken to be the structural transformation of an economy by Introducing more mechanized and updated technologies to increase labor productivity employment, incomes, and standard of living of the population Economic development should be accompanied by improvements in infrastructure as well as social, political, and institutional factors to facilitate transformation of the economy (Krueger, 2016). Economic development is regarded as important for a country to reduce its poverty by providing more employment, higher incomes. improved goods and services, and applications of latest technologies in production.

Economic development can be defined as efforts a that seek to improve the economic well-being and quality of life for a community by creating and/or retaining jobs and supporting or growing incomes and the base It is a sustained community effort to improve both the local economy and the quality of life by building area's capacity to adapt to economic change (Loveeidge and Morse 2016) Economic development encompasses job and income growth, sustainable increase in the productivity of individuals, businesses and resources to increase the overall wellbeing of citizens and quality of life. In achieving economic development. Salmon Valley Business and Innovation Centre have given three broad areas that must be taken seriously. They include:

- a) Policies that governments undertake to meet broad economic objectives such as price stability, high employment, expanded tax base. and sustainable growth. Such efforts include monetary and fiscal policies, regulation of financial institutions, trade, and tax policies.Policies and programme to provide
- b) infrastructure and services such as highways, parks, affordable housing, crime prevention, and educational programmes and projects.
- c) Policies and programme explicitly directed at job creation and retention through specific efforts in business finance, marketing, neighborhood development, small business start-up and development, business retention and expansion, technology transfer, workforce training and real estate development. This third category is a primary focus of economic development professionals.

4. **The Concept of Socio-economic Development**

This may refer to the transformation of a society with regards to social and economic dimensions. Socio-economic development incorporates public concerns in

developing social policy and economic initiatives. The ultimate objective of social development is to bring about sustained improvement in the well-being of the individual, groups, family, community, and society at large. It involves sustained increase in the economic standard of living of a country's population, normally accomplished by increasing its stocks of physical and human capital and thus improving its technology.

Socio-economic development is the progressive reinforcement of a socio-economic organization's quantitative and qualitative dimensions towards a higher level of efficiency, well-being, justice, and democracy at all levels. The socio-economic development is a process of quantitative, qualitative, and structural changes as a result of actions undertaken as part of societal (economic) practice. These changes affect material living conditions, economic structure and entrepreneurship, access to public goods and services, relations within a social system, the condition of the natural environment, and life. Liwinski (2017). Thus, the socio-economic development can generally be defined as a process of changes or improvement to social and economic conditions that affect an individual, organization, or an entire country (Weistroffer, 2016).

Generally, development is defined as a state in which things are improving. But it is defined in different ways in various contexts, social, political, biological, science and technology, language and literature. In the socio-economic context, development means the improvement of people's lifestyles through improved education, incomes, skills development and employment. It is the process of economic and social transformation based on cultural and environmental factors. Socio-economic development, therefore, is the process of social and economic development in a society.

It is measured with indicators, such as gross domestic product (GDP), life expectancy, literacy, and levels of employment. For a better understanding of socio-economic development, we may understand the meaning of social and economic development separately. Social development is a process that results in the transformation of social institutions in a manner that improves the capacity of the society to fulfill its aspirations. It implies a qualitative change in the way the society shapes itself and carries out its activities, such as through more progressive attitudes and behavior by the population, the adoption of more effective processes, or more advanced technology. There is a close relation between environments, ways of living, and technology. Economic development is the development of the economic wealth of countries or regions for the well-being of their inhabitants. It is the process by which a nation improves the economic, political, and social wellbeing of its people.

5. Effects of banditry on socio-economic development

Banditry in Nigeria jeopardizes the Nigerian agricultural system. Agriculture in Nigeria has not only produced food for Nigerians, but also produce raw materials for Nigerians industries. When bandit kills farmers and also forces those that are alive out of their farm settlement areas, the agricultural system crumble. This study also shows the significant negative consequences on poverty, unemployment, food security, education, health, income and general standard of living in the state and social activities of the states these acts of cattle rustling and armed banditry has caused a lot of hardship and state of fear amongst the residents of the states As argued by Bello (2017), communities like Kwokeye, Bingi, Kizara, Mashema, Maji, Fanda, Haki, Matankari, YarkKatsina and many communities in Maru, Anka, Gusau, Chafe, Birnin Magaji and Zurmi Local Governments were grossly affected. Apart from cattle rustling sometimes, women faced constant intimidation and harassment including cases of rape and assault while children are forced to embark on unprepared migration due to the fear of the unknown gun men. As argued by Shehu (2017), they sexually harassed women. Sometimes they would ask a resident to take his daughter or wife to their camp to rape and no one dares to stop them.

From 2015 to date, no accurate statistics could be provided as to the number of people killed through this act of armed banditry. As argued by Tukur (2017), people are killed in communities that are not even known to the security agencies and because of the nature of our community settlements, not all cases are reported especially those that involved Fulani herders. Bello (2017) makes an attempt to highlight some flashpoints that are termed as victims of this banditry. The undesired migration of Fulani and their cattle out of some affected areas in Zamfara to neighboring countries of Nigeria has serious socio-economic implications for the country. Tukur (2017) as cited in Anka (2017) noted that it cost a whole lot of money coupled with stress/risk to import cows from neighboring countries for consumption, aside from dairy and manure for farming activities, Socio-economic development has been brought to its

knees by these acts of banditry especially in Zamfara and other neighbouring states. According to Maureen and Blessing (2018) these security threats have great impact for Nigeria's socio-economic development. The instances below: shows the implications of these threats for Nigeria's socio-economic progress. It also shows the security threats and a few selected incidences and captures a few implications for Nigeria's socio-economic development.

- April 2018 Ejalah Vincent A. was attacked and scammed the amount of 300,000.
- May 2018, Mallam Yahaya (a poor farmer) attacked and defrauded of N57,000
- January 2019
- Angela Ngalburah transferred \$100,000 to some gangs of armed bandits who threatened her life.
- Shola Seni was equa

- Ily attacked, and later paid N200.000 as ransom.
 - June 2019 Mamman Auta was defrauded of N150,000
- (i) A report by the National Communication Commission in 2019 indicated that there has been a low inflow of foreign direct investment into the country This problem has been attributed to continued bandits' attacks on foreign investors in the country which has since succeeded in scaring away foreign investors and discouraging others from coming to invest in Nigeria. This means that there will be continuous less inflow of funds which may directly affect social and economic development in the country.
- (ii) The activities of these famous bandits have created a bad image for the country as information coming from Nigeria is frequently regarded as scam This means that Nigeria's financial institutions may not get full attention, and may likely be considered as an insecure country Nigerians are therefore undergoing serious scrutiny when establishing a business with other countries.

6. **Effects of banditry on economic and commercial sphere**

Armed banditry has become very common phenomenon in the country. In essence, most participants interviewed, confirmed that they had experienced the phenomenon at different times in their various communities, and, they will continue to recount the devastating effects that banditry acts have in both their physical, social, economic and psychological realms. "banditry has wrecked a lot of havoc on socio-economic development of Zamfara State" (Anas, 2020),

In fact, more than seventy (70) markets were closed for many years in the state due to activities of bandits. There was a specific market in one of the local governments in the state in which ten (10) trucks of animals were, everyday transported to the southwest part of the country for their meat consumptions but, today, with banditry. the people of Zamfarastate had to import animals as far as Adamawa and Borno states to be able to meet their daily meat consumptions. Due to the security threat caused by banditry in the state, the government from 2015 to 2021 claimed to be spending eight (8) billion naira per annum to security activities in the affected states. To him, these large sums of money could have been channeled to other developmental projects if not for this security challenges bedeviling the state. Moreover, (Yusuf, 2020) also explained that, even some of the policies introduced from 2015 to 2019 to curtail banditry had led to the collapse of many small seale businesses in the country To him. these small businesses were the engine through which some state economy flourished, for example, the Okada (motorcycle) riders in the state that were faced with motorcycle curfew and which many of them were their sole means of livelihood. The above is also the position of many respondents (Bello, 2020, and Bello, 2020) where they assert that Zamfara State is an agrarian society and bandits have since

barred the farmers from tilling the farm land, this have a greater effect on the people and the economy of the state

Moreover, it was estimated that, Zamfara State have thirty-eight thousand (38,000) hectares of land, and out of which about thirteen (13,000) thousand hectares were destroyed by bandits (Mohammed, 2019). This has, rendered most of the local farmers unemployed and un-productive, and the investors were afraid of coming for comunercialization, above all, businesses are no longer going on. By implication banditry had a very severe effect on the people and the economy of affected states and Nigerian as a whole. Maman, 2020. This had crippled the economy of many people in various communities and the state in general; this is because many farmers could not afford to pay the exorbitant amount placed on them, hence, many farm lands were left fallowed without cultivation.

The forceful relegation of the farm lands by farmers soon brought about the shortage of food for consumption by the teaming population as well as the hike in the general price of food commodities in the state. It was further estimated that, in 2015 alone, more than two (2000) thousand people were displaced in the state. In economic terms, these people are the capable hands that will turn around the economy of the state (Shinkafi, and Zugu, 2020). Mohammed, (2019) noted that schools have been destroyed and so most students do not go to school. Parents are not able to send their children to far schools due to fear of being kidnapped or killed by the armed bandits, Mohammed further noted that socio-economic activities have been crippled as people are living in constant fear of the unknown

(iii). Cases of rape has continued to be on the increase and constitute another setback in the socioeconomic development of the affected areas. Badaru (2017) argued that since 2014, there have been recorded cases of rape along the Dansadau forest by the armed bandits.

(iv). Onuah and Akwagyram (2019), reported that mining activities have been suspended in Zamfara due to frequent attacks by armed bandits. The implication of the suspension is that revenue generated through mining in the state has been cut off. and this may likely affect the aggregate economy in the country.

The cumulative number of deaths from May 2011 (when NST launched) to May 2015. when President Buhari was sworn-in for his first term, was 34,972 deaths and it has been on the increase, except for 2017, when the figures reduced before rising (again), By May 2016, Buhari's first year in office, an additional 8,388 people had been killed in Nigeria, bringing the tally to 43,310 deaths. The death rate slowed in 2017 by 4,949, about 40 percent, before increasing the following year, 2018, and recording 5,361 deaths. By May 2019. the number of deaths had risen again by 8,663

and by May 2020 it was 8,800 deaths even in a year of national lockdowns. This time the death tally had become 71,083. By May 2021, an additional 9,243 people had been killed in Nigeria and of the time of this report in May 2022, the tally had increased by 9,594, bringing total deaths due to violence to 89,920 in Nigeria

Example of killing of farmers by bandits took place at Yargamji village of Bataan LGA where on 6 July, 2020, famers were on the farm working after an overnight rain, the bandits numbering over 200 shot sporadically killing 15 farmers and injuring several others (Amnu, 2020). On 10th September, 2020, three famers were also killed by bandits in Dandume LGA, one of the most agrarian areas in the state (Erezi, 2020) In fact, most of the people killed by the bandits in the villages of the five LGAs are either farmers or cattle rearers whose death means their families and dependents suffered from food shortage at the family level which in turn affect food shortage in the country at large.

Farmers or cattle rearers have no option than to move to internally displaced persons camps where their source of food could be guaranteed for some time by the Government. Kidnapping of farmers is another devastating impact of banditry. where farmers were kidnapped when they go to the farm to work. In case where famers were kidnapped, they were taken to the forest and will not be released till large sums of money are paid as ransom. This payment of ransom impoverishes the famers and in some cases the farmers had no option but to sell their properties including their farmlands to get money to pay ransom. In Dandume LGA some of the farmers in the villages sold their farmlands to buy a house at Dandume town to escape kidnapping One of the most recent cases of kidnapping was at Malamawa village of Jiba LGA on 4th October 2020, where 22 farmers working on the farmlands were kidnapped while some managed to escape (Ibrahim. 2020). One of the farmers that narrowly escaped lamented that: "In these villages, we depend mostly on two things as source of livelihood farming and cattle rearing. Farming has become difficult due to insecurity Domestic animal rearing has also become difficult as bandits have rustled our cattle and presently they are abducting us on our farms"

Theoretical Framework

1. Theory of Human Needs

This research work made use of Theory of Human Needs as its theoretical framework. Human Needs theory generally proposed that all human beings have certain basic universal needs and that whenever these needs are denied, conflict is likely to occur. The theory was generally popularized by Maslow (1954), Burton Rosenberg (1984) and Maxneef (1991).

These theorists all agreed that the basic cause of most of the intractable conflict was the underlying need of people to meet their needs which can either be individual. groups and societal based. Human needs are very essential as this will help every

human to live and attain some level of well-being in any fit of any ramification of life. Hence the position of means the human needs theory to meet the needs of individual conflict. is that the unavailability any alterna or group is usually what triggere violence

Violence also might occur when humans require understwater and shelter consideration for their needs. Then heeds are not only food, water and shelter, be also biological needs such as participation, identification, understanding and elements that are for a successful Human growth and development, as well as those thand plusans are likely driven to tas now (2003) Maslow had earlier identified and placed those needs in a hito attain Sandra (200 in each need has specific ranking or order of attainment.

Primary physiological needs are, food, water and shelter. These are followed by the need for safety and security, and then followed by belonging or love, self-esteers and finally rounding up by enumerating personal fulfilment.

Safety/Security-The need for structure stability and freedom from fear and anxiety
Belongingness/Love-The needs to be accepted by others and to have strong personal tie with one's family, friends and identify groups.

Esteem needs are the fourth level in Maslow's hierarchy and include self-worth, accomplishment and respect. Maslow classified esteem needs into two categories:

- i esteem for oneself (dignity, achievement, mastery, independence) and
 - ii. the desire for reputation or respect from others (e.g., status, prestige).
- Maslow indicated that the need for respect or reputation is most important for children and adolescents and precedes real self-esteem or dignity.

Self-actualization needs are the highest level in Maslow's hierarchy, and refer to the realization of a person's potential, self-fulfilment, seeking personal growth and peak experiences. Maslow (1943) describes this level as the desire to accomplish everything that one can, to become the most that one can be

2. The Relevance of Human Needs Theory to this Work

Furthermore, the above theory is relevant to this research work in the sense that the theory was propounded to address issues that are conflict in nature, and in this context, it is unarguable fact that almost every part of Nigeria is currently grappling with the menace of armed banditry which had generally and negatively affected the

socio economic development of the country. Nigeria is now completely faced with an unending violent and conflict from armed banditry. Human Needs Theory tends to offer a new dimension to conflict theory. This is because the approach provides an important conceptual framework which does not only connects but also addresses human needs at all levels. In essence, Human Needs Theory is believed to have come to the force because of the range of frustration of basic human need as a threat to peace and social order. Conflict postulates on how universal human needs are often neglected, causing groups to employ the use of violence to claim their rights and satisfy their needs. Given more clarity to the above argument, Coate and Rosati (1988), assert that, human needs are powerful sources of explanation of human behavior and social interaction. They argued that, all individuals have needs they always strive to attain or satisfy.

Furthermore, this Theory is relevant to this work in the sense that the theory was propounded to address issues that are conflict in nature, and in this context, it is an unarguable fact that Zamfara, Kaduna and State are currently face with the menace of armed bandits which had negatively affected the socio-economic and human development in the country. The states are now completely ensued with an unending violent and conflict between farmers, herders, villagers and armed bandits. Importantly, is the issue of basic needs and interest. This tends to be the cardinal or pivotal caused of banditry and conflict in Zamfara State and others affected states in Nigeria. For instance, one of the arguments proffered by the segment f the society in Nigeria is the itemization of human needs theory, which was the issue of safety and security. The genesis of conflict in 2011 was the killing of a Fulani herdsman who was caught stealing in the village market. This killing, therefore, led to many rampant and simultaneous killing of many Fulani herdsman in various places in the State. For their safety and security, the Fulani herdsman gathered and engaged in a reprisal attacks and killings of farmers and villagers with a view to defending themselves and their stocks. Anka (2018).

In the same vein the relevance of the human needs theory could further be attributed to the inability of the government to provide the basic essential services for human survival. In fact, the inability of the Federal government to make adequate provision of social amenities in most of the affected communities had largely been the cause of conflict in most of the state in Nigeria. It is a fact that most of the villages in the country suffered and neglected in terms of provision of basic social amenities. These basic needs include food and good drinking water, health services, habitable environmental, job creation and financial incentives. Above all, there is an issue of high unemployment rate in the State which had been major issue in Nigeria society. These are some of the basic needs of individual which can cause conflict. Moreover, the United Nations Development program (UNDP, 1994) had identified 7 threats to

human security which can generally cause conflict in any society. The identified threats are economic threats, food threats, health threats, environmental threats, personal threats, community threats and political threats. Onaedo, Samuel, and John (2017).

Research Methodology

1. Research Design

This study employed survey research design. The sample analysis approach entailed the selection of a portion of the whole population for data collection and analysis using sampling techniques. Generalizations were made based on the result or finding. The approach was considered appropriate since data was gathered directly from those that were directly involved in the analysis. These details were important to the study question. The qualitative aspect of the study provided an answer to the only research question.

2. Population of the study

The design of this study involved data collection from individuals who are most likely familiar with banditry and other terrorist activities in Nigeria. As such, this research concentrated on farmers and their customers, the traders (particularly, those who buy farm products directly from places such as Katsina, Kaduna and Zamfara); military and police officers; civil and public servants who have adequate knowledge about Nigeria's current security situation. The informants were chosen based on their perceived expertise and willingness to be consulted about the topic under investigation. The participants were estimated at one thousand three hundred (1300).

3. Sample size and sampling technique

This study made use of simple random sampling technique to ensure that each element of the population had an equal probability of being chosen, and it selected 306 respondents who were either students or professionals, or even traditional rulers, but who had vast knowledge of insecurity and terrorism, particularly banditry. It would be noted that a sample is a representative subset of a population, and since the population for this analysis was estimated at one thousand three hundred (1300), 306 respondents, being the sample size was determined using the Taro Yamani formulas illustrated below.

Therefore, the Taro Yamani formula is represented below as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where, N-Population of the Study

n = Sample Size

(e) Level of significance. Note (e) = 0.05 (95%).

1 - Unit (a constant)

$$n = \frac{1300}{1 + 1300(e)}$$

$$n = \frac{1300}{1 + 1300(0.05)}$$

$$n = \frac{1300}{1300(0.0025)}$$

$$n = 1300 \times 0.0025 = 3.25$$

$$n = \frac{1300}{1 + 3.25}$$

$$n = \frac{1300}{4.25}$$

$$n = \mathbf{306}$$

4. Research Instrument

The data used in this study were drawn from both primary and secondary sources. A personally structured questionnaire was compiled, duplicated and distributed to the relevant respondents. In other words, the primary data was obtained through the issuing of 350 copies of questionnaires, and retrieval of 306 copies of the forms. The questionnaire, with which the researcher introduced both the topic to and encouraged the respondents in the proper ways of providing answers to the questions on the questionnaire were handed over to the relevant respondents for this purpose.

5. Validity and reliability of the instrument

The instrument was validated through the scrutiny of the draft by our peer reviewers and supervisors. Their comments, criticisms and corrections reshaped the original contents of the questionnaire. All the corrections made were reflected in the final draft of the instrument. The instrument was also subjected to the researchers' test-retest method in establishing a reliability of the instrument. The researchers administered the questionnaire forms twice to the respondents. It was within one week interval, that the same questionnaire was administered to the same set of respondents. The closeness of the responses gathered from the two sets of administered questionnaire was matched to further help to establish the reliability of the instrument.

6. Method of data collections

For the primary source of data, questionnaire, in-depth interviews (IDI) and

Focused Group Discussions (FGD) were used. But, for the secondary sources of data, review of related records such as written and classified materials like textbooks, newspapers, magazines, journals, conference papers and the internet were used.

7. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using Chi-square to test the formulated hypotheses.

Therefore, the chi-square formula is given below as:

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-e)^2}{e}$$

Where X^2 = Chi-square

= Summation

O=Observation.

Decision Rule (Statistical Decision)

When the calculated X^2 value is greater than the critical table value, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted and when the calculated X^2 value is less than the critical table value, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is rejected.

Item 1: Effect of banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria

The table below tabulates and analyses six (6) variables on the vertical strand, namely: traders, farmers, displaced persons, migrants and foreign investors using the Likert's scale on the horizontal strand for measurement in the order of SA, A, SD and U to find the resultant total percentage of responses from the various categories of respondents. But for the purposes of maintaining the required limit and scope of the research, the researcher was restricted to treating only column number two, which is farmers that have to do with agricultural production in Nigeria.

Table 1.

Variables	SA	A	SD	D	U	TOTAL
Traders	160 (53.2%)	86 (28.1%)	19 (6.2%)	13 (4.2%)	28 (9.2%)	306 (100%)
Farmers	154 (50%)	86 (38.1%)	8 (3.3%)	24 (7.9%)	34 (11.1%)	306 (100%)
Displaced persons	110 (35.9%)	102 (33.8%)	19 (6.2%)	48 (15.6%)	27 (9.0%)	306 (100%)
Migrants	81 (26.5%)	146 (47.7%)	41 (13.1%)	13 (4.2%)	25 (8.2%)	306 (100%)

Foreign investors	189 (61.8%)	64 (24.9%)	2 (0.7%)	20 (6.5%)	28 (9.2%)	306 (100%)
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Source: Field work, 2023.

Table 1 above shows that 160 (53.2%) of total number of 306 (100%) respondents among the traders, strongly agreed that banditry has strong negative consequences on agricultural production in Nigeria; 86 (28.1%) agreed to the fact; 19 (6.2%) strongly disagreed; 13 (4.2%) disagreed; and 28 (9.2%) were undecided.

Under farmers' column, 154 (50%) of total number of 306 (100%) respondents strongly agreed that banditry has strong negative consequences on agricultural production in Nigeria; 86 (38.1%) agreed; 8 (3.3%) strongly disagreed; 24 (7.9%) disagreed; 34 (11.1%) were undecided.

As regards displaced persons, 110 (35.9%) of total number of 306 (100%) respondents strongly agreed that banditry has strong negative consequences on agricultural production in Nigeria; 102 (33.8%) agreed; 19 (6.2%) strongly disagreed; 48 (15.6%) disagreed; 27 (9.0%) were undecided.

Under migrants, 81 (26.5%) of total number of 306 (100%) respondents strongly agreed that banditry has strong negative consequences on agricultural production in Nigeria; 146 (44.7%) agreed; 41 (13.1%) strongly disagreed; 13 (4.2%) disagreed; 25 (8.2%) were undecided.

In the last lap, which is foreign investors, 189 (61.8%) of the total number of 306 (100%) respondents strongly agreed that banditry has strong negative consequences on agricultural production in Nigeria; 64 (21.9%) agreed; 2 (0.7%) strongly disagreed; 20 (6.5%) disagreed; 28 (9.2%) were undecided.

Item 2: What are the effects of banditry on agricultural production in Nigeria?

Table 2.

Responses	No. of Respondents	Percentage
SA	160	
A	86	
SD	19	
D	13	
U	28	
TOTAL	306	

Source: Field work, 2023.

Table 2 above shows that 160 (53.2%) of total number of 306 (100%) respondents among the traders, strongly agreed that banditry has strong negative consequences on agricultural production in Nigeria; 86 (28.1%) agreed to the fact; 19 (6.2%) strongly disagreed; 13 (4.2%) disagreed; and 28 (9.2%) were undecided.

Testing of Hypothesis

H₁: The effect of banditry seems to be negative on agricultural production in Nigeria.

H₀: The effect of banditry seems not to be negative on agricultural production in Nigeria.

$$\frac{\sum(\text{fo}-\text{fe})^2}{\text{fe}}$$

fo = Observed frequency

fe = Expected frequency

∑ = Summation

Table 3

Responses from the respondents	SA	A	SD	D	U	Total
	86	23	30	10	7	156
	50	40	30	20	10	150
Total	136	63	60	30	17	306

Source: *Field work, 2023*

$$\text{fe} = \frac{(\text{column total})(\text{row total})}{\text{grand total}}$$

$$\text{Cell A} = \frac{156 \times 136}{306} = 69.3$$

$$\text{Cell B} = \frac{156 \times 63}{306} = 32.1$$

$$\text{Cell C} = \frac{156 \times 60}{306} = 30.6$$

$$\text{Cell D} = \frac{156 \times 30}{306} = 15.3$$

$$\text{Cell E} = \frac{156 \times 17}{306} = 8.7$$

$$\text{Cell F} = \frac{150 \times 136}{306} = 66.7$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cell G} &= \frac{150 \times 63}{306} = 30.9 \\ \text{Cell H} &= \frac{150 \times 60}{306} = 29.4 \\ \text{Cell I} &= \frac{150 \times 30}{306} = 14.7 \\ \text{Cell J} &= \frac{150 \times 17}{306} = 8.3 \end{aligned}$$

Table 4: Chi-Square (X^2)

Cell	fo	fe	fo- fe	(fo-fe) ²	$\frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$
A	86	69.3	16.7	278.9	4.02
B	23	32.1	-9.1	17.28	0.5
C	30	30.6	-0.6	0.36	11.0
D	10	15.3	-5.3	28.09	1.8
E	7	8.7	-1.7	2.89	0.3
F	50	66.7	-16.7	278.9	4.2
G	40	30.9	9.1	17.28	0.6
H	30	29.4	0.6	0.36	0.01
I	20	14.7	5.3	28.09	1.9
J	10	8.3	1.7	2.89	0.3
					$\sum X^2 = 24.63$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (C - 1)(R - 1) \\ &= (5-1) \times (2-1) \\ &= 4 \times 1 = 4 \end{aligned}$$

Level of significance = 0.05

Calculated value = 24.68

Critical table value = 9.49

Decision Rule:

Decision rule means that when the calculated value is greater than critical value, the null hypothesis will be rejected, while the alternate hypothesis will be accepted, and vice versa. In that case since the calculated value of 24.63 is greater than the critical table value of 9.49 at 0.05 level of significance at 4 degree of freedom in the above calculation, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is

accepted, which means that the effects of banditry is negative on agricultural production in Nigeria.

Discussion on findings

This work, made this singular finding:

This research has helped to unravel the activities of banditry and how they have impacted on socio-economic development in Nigeria. The impact was seen in the area of farming, trading, displacement, migration and the fears it brought on foreign investors from coming into the country for investments. In line with that, it was found that banditry activities have extreme negative consequences on socio-economic development in Nigeria. Maman (2020), assert that banditry has rendered most of the local farmers unemployed and un-productive; and the investors were afraid of coming for commercialization, above all, businesses are no longer going on. By implication, banditry had a very severe effect on the people and the economy of affected states and Nigeria as a whole.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

Based on the above summation, it is generally established that banditry has been the bane of development in Nigeria as its heinous activities have led to the total suspension of many socio-economic activities in the affected states of the Federation. This action has dispersed farmers; caused untold hardship and unintentional fleeing from those affected states; foreign investors have refused to come into the country for investments; and so forth. Moreover, on the issue of farming, in which farming activities abound in the villages, banditry activities in state such as Borno, Katsina, Kaduna and Zamfara have made many farmers to abandon their farm lands and run away for the safety of their lives and those of their family members to some safer places to avoid dangers.

3. Recommendation

Unarguably, the fact that armed banditry has posed serious threat to Nigerian national security; this is evident on how the group had over the years, engaged in violent attacks, kidnaping, assassinations, rape, and destruction of lives and properties in the country. Therefore, the following recommendation was made to help curb the issue of banditry in Nigeria.

Based on the finding of this research which was that banditry has a strong negative effect on agricultural production in Nigeria, government should employ proactive measures based on international best practices like training and retraining of officers; total overhauling and equipping of the military forces with world-class ammunitions; deployment and redeployment of officers from their military base, etc. in order to

reduce the strength, if not to completely exterminating banditry from farm lands in Nigeria, particularly in the northern part of the country.

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